

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Bimetallic Mixed Cyanate Selenocyanate Complexes $M(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2$ [$M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$] and their Lewis Acid Behaviour towards Number of Bases

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$\text{Ti}_2(\text{SeCN})_4$ and $M(\text{NCO})_2$ (where $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II}) interact to produce $M(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2$, which combine with tetrahydrofuran, methanol, dimethylsulphoxide and acetone (L) to form polymeric bridged complexes of the type $[>L_2M(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2<]_n$ and with pyridine nicotinamide, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10 phenanthroline to form cationic-anionic complexes of the type $[\text{ML}_2]^{2+}[\text{Ti}(\text{SeCN})(\text{OCN})]_2^-$. Spectral and magnetic data reveal that Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are octahedral in all the complexes, except in $\text{Co}(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2$, where Co^{II} is tetrahedral. The nature of bonding has been explained by Pearson's HSAB principle and Klopman's softness calculations. T.G.A. shows decomposition of ligands earlier than cyanate and selenocyanate. Most of the compounds are found fungitoxic and antibacterial towards soil fungi and soil bacteria.

BIMETALLIC tetrathiocyanates, tetraselenocyanates and mixed dithiocyanatodiselenocyanates, and their complexes have been well studied^{1-8,14}. However, such studies have not been made on bimetallic tetracyanates, dicyanatodithiocyanates and dicyanatodiselenocyanates. Only a few simple cyanate complexes have been reported in literature^{1,7-9}. The established bonding modes of this ion are through N-end ($M-\text{NCO}$), O-end ($M-\text{OCN}$)

and bridging $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{M} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{NCO} \end{array}\right)^{3,4}$. Recently⁹⁻¹¹, end-to-

end bridging of the type ($M-\text{NCO}-M$) has been established by X-ray analysis in some bridged cyanate complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} . In order to find out the mode of cyanate and selenocyanate bonding in dicyanatodiselenocyanate complexes, we have prepared some of them and their adducts with various oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands. Due to potential fungicidal and antibacterial activities of cyanate and selenocyanate ions their antimicrobial action has also been studied.

Experimental

All reagents were of B.D.H. or E. Merk grade and were used after purification and drying by standard methods⁹. Ligands were used after recrystallisation from ethanol. All solvents were used after redistillation and drying. TiSeCN was prepared by the reported method⁵.

$M(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2$ [$M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$]: A solution of $M(\text{NCO})_2$ (1 mmol) was prepared in dry alcohol by stirring the metal nitrate (1 mmol) and potassium cyanate overnight. Precipitated pota-

ssium nitrate was filtered off, and to the filtrate TiSeCN (2 mmol) was added and stirred for ~ 28 h. Decomposition of selenocyanate was avoided by making the contents slightly alkaline with KOH. The resulting green precipitated product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

$M(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2 \cdot 6\text{py}$: To a suspension of $M(\text{NCSe})_2\text{Ti}_2(\text{OCN})_2$ (1 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml), pyridine (py; 6 mmol) was added and stirred for ~ 24 h. A pink complex was formed in the case of Co^{II} and green in case of Ni^{II} . The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by acetone and ether, and dried in vacuum under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

Similarly, nicotinamide (nia), phenanthroline (phen) and bipyridyl (bipy) adducts were prepared. The adducts with THF, DMSO, MeOH and acetone were prepared by stirring the Lewis acid in these solvents for ~ 36 h. The DMSO complex was recovered by evaporating the solvent while others were precipitated and recovered by filtration and drying under reduced pressure.

The complexes were analysed for Co as anthranilate, Se as the metal, Ni as DMG complex and Ti as thalious chromate. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Satisfactory analytical results were obtained for all the complexes (Table 1).

Activity of compounds on soil fungi and soil bacteria: Activity of compounds on soil fungi was tested using 0.01M aqueous solutions (1 ml) in each dish containing 1 ml of soil suspension (0.1 mg) by dilution plate method¹⁰ on molten Czapek's media (15 ml). A reference dish was made without addition of any test compound. All dishes were well

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			Co/Ni	Tl	Se	N		
A	Green	165	7.61 (7.75)	53.45 (53.61)	20.40 (20.78)	7.20 (7.35)	4.18	92.12
A.2MeOH	Light pink	162	7.02 (7.15)	49.16 (49.45)	19.00 (19.15)	6.56 (6.78)	4.93	40.78
A.2Acetone	Pink	158	6.52 (6.72)	46.12 (46.52)	18.00 (18.21)	6.18 (6.38)	4.92	41.52
A.2dmso	Pink	145	5.92 (6.13)	44.21 (44.49)	17.10 (17.21)	5.98 (6.10)	4.98	50.56
A.6py	Pink	155	4.60 (4.77)	32.75 (33.03)	12.60 (12.79)	11.16 (11.33)	5.12	128.86
A.6nia	Pink	160	3.56 (3.95)	27.10 (27.32)	10.12 (10.58)	14.83 (15.12)	5.02	45.86
A.3bipy	Pink	162	4.12 (4.80)	32.09 (33.19)	12.62 (12.85)	10.86 (11.30)	4.98	197.70
A.3phen	Brown	190	4.08 (4.85)	29.82 (30.12)	10.65 (11.16)	10.07 (10.88)	5.10	124.20
A.2thf	Pink	148	5.05 (4.91)	44.88 (45.03)	17.02 (17.45)	6.15 (6.18)	5.02	45.86
B	Green	185	7.42 (7.62)	53.08 (53.61)	20.42 (20.76)	7.16 (7.35)	3.20	42.56
B.2MeOH	Green	190	6.96 (7.03)	48.88 (49.51)	19.06 (19.17)	6.52 (6.79)	3.08	48.76
B.2Acetone	Green	162	6.52 (6.62)	45.91 (46.57)	17.96 (18.08)	6.20 (6.31)	3.10	40.26
B.2thf	Green	156	6.31 (6.41)	45.10 (45.18)	17.30 (17.47)	6.12 (6.19)	3.20	45.60
B.6py	Green	196	4.52 (4.70)	32.96 (33.06)	12.62 (12.80)	11.12 (11.84)	3.10	127.80
B.6nia	Green	182	3.58 (3.86)	27.19 (27.34)	10.27 (10.58)	14.96 (15.01)	2.98	132.10
B.3phen	Green	180	4.14 (4.28)	30.02 (30.13)	12.01 (11.86)	10.45 (10.33)	3.00	122.70
B.3bipy	Green	185	4.36 (4.72)	32.87 (33.23)	13.01 (12.86)	11.23 (11.40)	3.01	128.50

*A = Co(NCSe)₂Tl₂(OCN)₂, B = Ni(NCSe)₂Tl₂(OCN)₂.

covered and left for 48 h at room temperature (25–38°). Peptone beef extract Agar media (15 ml) was used in each petri dish and pH adjusted to 7. The percentage inhibition was calculated as described earlier²¹.

Physical measurements: All complexes were found to decompose without melting and were apparently insoluble in common organic solvents except DMF and DMSO. Molar conductance values of the complexes were recorded in DMF on a Philips PR-9500 conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a SP-300 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000–200 cm⁻¹ and electronic spectra (nujol) on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer in the range 2 500–200 nm. Magnetic susceptibility values were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CoHg(SCN)₄ as calibrant. Pascal's constants were used for diamagnetic corrections.

Results and Discussion

Lewis Acids M(NCSe)₂Tl₂(OCN)₂ [M = Co^{II} or Ni^{II}]: Two absorption bands are found in the electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complex at 16 600 and 9 520 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) and

⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(ν₂) transitions, respectively, showing Co^{II} in an octahedral environment in its complex¹⁵. The magnitude of other spectral parameters, viz. Dq (575 cm⁻¹), B' (595 cm⁻¹) and β (0.96) and magnetic moment value (4.18 B.M.) also support this geometry¹⁶. Three bands in the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complex at 28 500, 16 600 and 9 690 cm⁻¹ are due to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁) transitions, respectively¹⁵ and magnetic moment value of 3.2 B.M. suggest Ni^{II} in an octahedral environment in its complex. The values of spectral parameters Dq (962 cm⁻¹), B' (942 cm⁻¹) and β (0.91) also support such coordination¹⁶.

The presence of two ir bands for each of ν_{CN}, ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} at 2 130–2 150, 580–595 and 380–390 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the complexes, indicates the presence of bridged selenocyanate groups^{6–8,19}. Two bands observed at 280–290 cm⁻¹ are due to ν_{M-NCS}, which are consistent with the reported positions for this band^{20–22}. Two bands in each, ν_{CN}, ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} regions of cyanate are observed at 2 230–2 250, 1 280–1 310 and 620–640 cm⁻¹, respectively, indicating the presence of end-to-end bridged cyanate (–NCO–) groups^{9–11,23}. Two bands are observed at 330–360 cm⁻¹ for ν_{M-NCO}.

Two bands in each region of cyanate and selenocyanate ions are observed due to splitting of ν_{M-NCX} ($X=Se$ or O) degenerate modes²¹⁻²⁴.

The various bonding modes of NCO and NCSe moieties shown here are also in agreement with the Pearson's HSAB principle¹² which predicts that the harder end of pseudohalide ion should be linked to the harder metal (M) and the softer end to the softer metal (Tl). Thus the harder N ends of NCSe and NCO coordinate to harder Co^{II} or Ni^{II} and the softer Se or O ends to Tl^I . A rough estimate of the softness values of the nitrogen and oxygen ends of cyanate ion by Klopman's method¹⁸, using Wagner's partial values of charges on each atom of cyanate ion²⁵, supports such conclusion. A polymeric bridged structure with alternate metal centers is proposed for the Lewis acids on the basis of the above results.

Polymetric bridged complexes $> L_2M(NCSe)_2-Tl_2(OCN)_2 < [M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}; L=MeOH, thf, dmsO, acetone]$: Analytical data (Table 1) show that two molecules of the ligands are attached to each molecule of Lewis acid in the complexes. Molar conductance values in dmf ($40.26-50.65 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) indicate their non-conducting nature. The Co^{II} complexes are pink while the Ni^{II} complexes green. Their magnetic moment values (Table I), electronic spectral band positions and spectral parameters indicate octahedral geometry around Ni^{II} or Co^{II} .

The ir band positions of the Lewis acids are not much changed on complexation. The slight changes in band position are due to the change of geometry around Co^{II} or Ni^{II} . On complex formation the ir bands due to ν_{CN} , ν_{CS_e} and δ_{NCS_e} of selenocyanate occur at 2 180-2 120, 595-580 and 395-370 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating the presence of bridged selenocyanate groups^{2,6,7,19}. Two bands in each, ν_{CN} , ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} of cyanate are observed at 2 265-2 230, 1 310-1 250 and 640-620 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating the presence of bridged cyanate groups^{4,7-10}. The position of ν_{Co-NCS_e} band, observed at 290 cm^{-1} in Lewis acid, is lowered by 10-20 cm^{-1} on complexation, indicating the change of coordination geometry from tetrahedral to octahedral^{19,21}. These adducts, therefore, possess structural similarity to the Lewis acids except with a difference that two ligand molecules are coordinated to Co^{II} or Ni^{II} . Coordination of ligands to Co^{II} or Ni^{II} in comparison to Tl^I takes place due to (i) the change in stereochemistry around Co^{II} from tetrahedral to octahedral on adduct formation, (ii) the presence of ν_{M-L} bands at 340-320 cm^{-1} and shifting of ν_{M-NCS_e} to lower frequency on adduct formation^{18,14}, (iii) the coordination of harder ligands to harder Co^{II} or Ni^{II} by HSAB principle and the higher values of $\Delta E_{nm}^{\ddagger}(M-L)$ compared to $\Delta E_{nm}^{\ddagger}(Tl-L)$ (Table 2), and (iv) higher values of total softness difference, $\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(M-Tl)$ obtained on considering ligand attached to Co^{II} or Ni^{II} compared to those obtained on considering ligand attached to Tl^I .

Cationic-anionic complexes $[ML_x]^{+2}[Tl(SeCN)(NCO)]_x^{-1}$ ($L=py, nia; x=6; L=bipy, phen; x=3$): Molar conductance values of the complexes in dimethylformamide are found in the range for 1:2 electrolytes. Colour, magnetic moment values (Table 1), electronic spectral band positions and spectral parameters show that $M(II)$ is octahedral in the complexes. Higher Dq values, obtained in these cases support the existence of $[M(L-L)_6]^{+2}$ or $[ML_6]^{+2}$ in pure O_h symmetry. Further, the harder ligands, which show features of coordination through ring nitrogen, coordinate to harder Co^{II} or Ni^{II} in preference to Tl^I according to HSAB principle¹².

The ir bands due to ν_{CN} , ν_{CS_e} and δ_{NCS_e} of selenocyanate ion appear at 2 120-2 090, 570-530 and 370-350 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating its terminal linkage through Se-end. The positions of ν_{CN} , ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} bands due to cyanate ion at 2 210-2 180, 1 365-1 320 and 690-620 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicate the presence of N-bonded terminal cyanates. Softer Se-end of selenocyanate and O-end of cyanate link to softer Tl^I by HSAB principle¹². The presence of ν_{Co-L} or ν_{Ni-L} bands at 330-300 cm^{-1} is also consistent with the formation of bimetallic complexes as reported earlier^{6,14}.

Quantitative softness values: The softness values of various metals and ligands present in the complexes were calculated by Klopman's equations^{6,18,24}. Metal-ligand coordination is favoured in the direction of higher values of $\Delta E_{nm}^{\ddagger}(M-L)$ ²⁶. This difference is expressed by

$$\Delta E_{nm}^{\ddagger}(M-L) = E_n^{\ddagger}(M) - E_m^{\ddagger}(L)$$

ΔE_{nm}^{\ddagger} values for both types of linkages, (M-L) and (Tl-L) have been calculated and presented in Table 2. The values of M-L interactions are found higher than those for Tl-L, favouring the attachment of ligands to $M(II)$.

Recently²⁷, the total softness difference, $\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(M-M')$ (matching constant), has been evaluated from total softness values, TE_n^{\ddagger} , around M and M' in $MM'(NCX)_4XL$ ($X=S$ or Se). Higher magnitude of matching constant is indicative of greater stability of pseudohalide bridge²⁶. The values of $\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(M-Tl)$ have been calculated (i) for the structure in which ligands are attached to $M(II)$ and (ii) for alternate structure in which ligands are supposed to attach with Tl^I by adopting the following equations,

$$(a) >L_2M(NCSe)_2Tl_2(OCN)_2 <$$

$$TE_n^{\ddagger}(M) = E_n^{\ddagger}(M) + 2E_m^{\ddagger}(NCSe) + 2E_m^{\ddagger}(L)$$

$$TE_n^{\ddagger}(Tl) = E_n^{\ddagger}(Tl) + E_m^{\ddagger}(SeCN) + E_m^{\ddagger}(OCN)$$

$$\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(M-Tl) = TE_n^{\ddagger}(M) - TE_n^{\ddagger}(Tl)$$

TABLE 2—CALCULATED SOFTNESS, SOFTNESS DIFFERENCE AND MATCHING CONSTANT VALUES

Compd.*	$E_m^\ddagger(L)^{**}$	ΔE_{nm}^\ddagger (Co-L)/(Ni-L)	$\Delta E_{nm}^\ddagger(Tl-L)$	$\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(Co-Tl)/(Ni-L)^{**}$	
				(a)	(b)
A.2thf	-11.69	10.02	9.54	53.42	17.13
A.2dmso	-10.86	10.21	8.71	51.76	18.76
A.6py	-11.75	11.08	9.60		54.14 ^a
A.6nia	-13.96	13.23	11.75		67.04 ^a
A.3bipy	-11.70	11.03	9.55		53.84 ^a
A.3phen	-11.98	11.21	9.83		55.52 ^a
B.2thf	-11.69	11.53	9.54	52.59	16.30
B.2dmso	-10.86	10.70	8.71	50.93	17.93
B.6py	-11.75	11.08	9.60		53.31 ^a
B.6nia	-13.90	13.23	11.75		66.21 ^a
B.3bipy	-11.70	11.03	9.55		53.01 ^a
B.3phen	-11.98	11.21	9.83		54.69 ^a

*A=Co(NCSe)₂Tl₂(OCN)₂, B=Ni(NCSe)₂Tl₂(OCN)₂. $E_m^\ddagger(NCSe^-) = -8.93$, $E_m^\ddagger(SeCN^-) = -4.41$ (Ref. 6), $E_m^\ddagger(NCO^-) = -14.27$, $E_m^\ddagger(OCN^-) = -10.47$ (Ref. 23) (all values in methanol medium), $E_n^\ddagger(Co^{2+}) = -0.67$, $E_n^\ddagger(Ni^{2+}) = 0.16$, $E_n^\ddagger(Tl^+) = -2.15$ (Ref. 26).

** (a) = Values obtained by considering ligand attached to Co^{II} or Ni^{II}; (b) = values for alternate structure where ligand is supposed to attach with Tl^I; ^a Values for cationic-anionic structure $[ML_x]^{2+}[Tl(SeCN)(OCN)]_2^-$ (M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}).

$$TE_n^\ddagger(M) = E_n^\ddagger(M) + 2E_m^\ddagger(NCO) + 2E_m^\ddagger(NCSe)$$

$$TE_n^\ddagger(Tl) = E_n^\ddagger(Tl) + E_m^\ddagger(SeCN) + E_m^\ddagger(L)$$

$$\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(M-Tl) = TE_n^\ddagger(M) - TE_n^\ddagger(Tl)$$

The $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(M-Tl)$ values calculated for the proposed structure (a) are found higher than those for (b) (Table 2), indicating the attachment of ligands to M(II) (M=Co^{II}, Ni^{II}).

Ligands of lower basicity, e.g. thf, dmso, MeOH or acetone are unable to break the chain forming polymeric bridged complexes, while those with higher basicity, e.g. py, nia, phen and bipy, break the bridge and form cationic-anionic complexes. Pyridine and nicotinamide form monomeric bridged complexes^{9,14} with MM'(NCS)₄ and MM'(NCSe)₄ while break in the bridge with the present complexes indicates lower stability of cyanate bridge compared to thiocyanate or selenocyanate bridge.

Thermogravimetric analysis: The T.G.A. curves of the complexes show three major inflections. First inflection lies in the range 140–250°, percent mass loss being equivalent to the loss of ligands (thf, dmso, MeOH, acetone, py, nia, phen or bipy). The percent mass loss in the second inflection (280–500°) is found nearly equivalent to the decomposition of the complex, M(NCSe)₂Tl₂(OCN)₂ to M(III) cyanides and thallos oxide. The percent mass loss in the third inflection (850–1000°) is found nearly equivalent to the decomposition of metal cyanides and thallos oxide to metals which is the actual decomposition range of these salts. Above this temperature, the mass loss almost ceases. On comparing T.G.A. curves of these complexes with those of the corresponding thiocyanate selenocyanate complexes^{9,14}, we find the first and second inflection ranges at lower positions, indica-

ting lower stability of cyanate bridge compared to the former.

Activity of compounds on soil fungi and soil bacteria: All the complexes were found to be highly toxic for soil fungi (100% inhibition). Co^{II} Lewis acid showed 85% inhibition while that of Ni^{II} 58% inhibition with reference to control. Fungitoxic nature of bimetallic cyanatoselenocyanates was found enhanced on complexation. All the complexes along with Lewis acids were found highly antibacterial (70–100% inhibition). Antibacterial nature of Ni^{II} Lewis acid and complexes was found greater than those of Co^{II}.

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